

Supporting Information

Electronic Structure Origins of Radical Character in Triangular Acenes: Sextet Stabilization vs. Antiaromaticity Release

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Table S1. Energy and $\langle S^2 \rangle$ considerations on DFT-optimized An and Tn series obtained at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) computational level.

n	Linear, An			Triangular, Tn		
	$\Delta E_{\text{UKS-RKS}}^a$	$\langle S^2 \rangle^b$	$\Delta E_{\text{S-T}}^c$	$\Delta E_{\text{UKS-RKS}}^a$	$\langle S^2 \rangle^b$	$\Delta E_{\text{S-T}}^c$
3	-	-	2.03	-	0.03	0.63
4	-	-	1.42	0.001	1.70	0.44
5	-	-	0.96	2.3	2.76	0.41
6	-	-	0.64	7.5	3.51	0.41
7	1.34	0.44	0.45	14.0	0.03	0.69

^aUKS-RKS stability differences in kcal/mol. ^b Expectation value of the S^2 upon UKS optimization.

^cAdiabatic vertical spin flip excitation energy between singlet and triplet states in eV.

Table S2. HOMO-LUMO energy gaps in eV of An and Tn series computed at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level.

n	An	Tn
3	5.48	3.24
4	4.56	2.79
5	3.90	2.75
6	3.41	2.73
7	3.37	2.97

Table S3. Calculated adiabatic (adiab) and vertical (vert) singlet-triplet energy gaps (in eV) computed at the M06-2X and RAS-SF levels for the An and Tn series.

n	M06-2X, adiab		M06-2X, vert		RAS-SF, vert	
	An	Tn	An	Tn	An	Tn
3	2.03	0.63	2.50	1.09	2.50	1.14
4	1.42	0.44	1.82	0.85	1.95	0.96
5	0.96	0.41	1.33	0.79	1.45	0.67
6	0.64	0.41	0.97	0.80	1.11	0.47
7	0.45	0.69	0.64	0.91	0.72	0.31

Figure S1. Pertinent bond lengths of the DFT-optimized structures of the T_n and A_n series. Bond lengths ≥ 1.50 are in blue, bond lengths < 1.40 are in red, while those in between are in purple.

Figure S2. RASCI(h,p)/6-31G(d,p) Computed states with RASCI (10 roots) for **T3**.

Figure S3. RASCI(h,p)/6-31G(d,p) Computed states with RASCI (10 roots) for **T4**.

Figure S4. RASCI(h,p)/6-31G(d,p) Computed states with RASCI (10 roots) for **T5**.

Figure S5. RASCI(h,p)/6-31G(d,p) Computed states with RASCI (10 roots) for **T6**.

Figure S6. RASCI(h,p)/6-31G(d,p) Computed states with RASCI (10 roots) for T6.

Figure S7. NICS(1) values calculated at the M062x/6-311++g(2d,p) level of theory on the DFT-optimized ground state structures.

Figure S8. NICS(1) values computed at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level at the center of the six-member rings in (a) A3, A3', T3; (b) A4, A4', T4; (c) A6, A6', T6 and; (d) A7, A7', T7 molecules.